

Phase change in porous media for heat exchanger applications

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Abstract

This work presents the definition of the porous model as well as its application. Firstly, we will present a sensitivity analysis of the model on the boundary conditions. The parameters required by the model will be extracted from a series of simulations to replace an experimental device. A volume average per fin element will be used to determine the mass transfer source term and hence the exchange coefficient.

Keywords: CFD, Porous media, Heat exchanger, Heat transfer, Mass transfer, Multiphase flow

1. Nomenclature

α : Volume fraction

t : Time

ϵ : Porosity

Y : Mass fraction

ρ : Density

e : Internal energy

E : Total energy

u : velocity

μ : Dynamic viscosity

P : Pressure

m : Mass

k_{eff} : Effective conductivity

\dot{m} : Mass transfer rate

μ_p : Pressure equilibrium coefficient

λ_v : Velocity equilibrium coefficient

H_T : Thermal equilibrium coefficient

C_p : Specific heat

λ : Conductivity

γ : Heat capacity ratio

k : Permeability

k_1 : Inertial permeability

L_{LV} : Latent heat

T_{sat} : Saturation temperature

P_{sat} : Saturation pressure

β : Inertial resistance coefficient

S : Surface

Nu : Nusselt number

Pr : Prandtl number

Re : Reynolds number

j : Colburn factor

f : Fanning friction factor

D_h : Hydraulic diameter

G : Mass flow rate

V : Volume of medium

V_f : Volume of fluid in medium

g : Chemical potential

A_I : Interfacial specific area

2. Introduction

In a general context of reducing energy consumption and production costs, heat exchangers have become a key element. CFD simulations based on the use of porous media are nowadays the most commonly encountered method for industrial applications to design and dimension heat exchangers with intensification structures such as fins. This enables the best compromise between numerical resource requirements and accuracy of results. In the case of two-phase flows, this is currently not a widespread approach.

This study is based on the use of a two-phase Eulerian mixing model solved by the StarCCM+ software. The pressure drop of the porous medium is modelled by a power law (Darcy-Forchheimer type) per phase. The porous medium is considered to be in thermal imbalance locally, resulting in the addition of a volume source term based on an exchange coefficient. This coefficient integrates heat and mass transfer. It can be spatially variable, reflecting the topology of the two-phase flow (bubble, slug, annular, etc.). We will first present a sensitivity analysis of the model. Different boundary conditions (mass flow, quality, heat flux) will be applied to estimate the influence of each parameter in our two-temperature porous model.

In a second step, we will extract the parameters required by the model from a series of locally resolved simulations (local simulations of a representative finned channel with phase change). A volume averaging method will be used to determine the mass transfer source term and hence the exchange coefficient. The influence of other parameters such as fin geometry or gravity orientation will also be studied. This new model will be applied to the simulation of an evaporator used in a steam cycle, operating with R134a.

3. State of the art

Different developments were made to simplify the numerical modelization of heat exchangers with porous media. In [1] a procedure for the optimization of heat exchanger geometry is developed. As a part of this program an integral numerical code for modeling of heat exchangers was constructed. The numerical code is derived from Whitaker's [2] presentation of the Volume Averaging Technique (VAT) for a porous media flow. The heat exchanger core can be treated as a porous media to expedite code and make it appropriate for surface optimization computations.

The internal structure of the heat exchanger is composed of isothermal tubes, and it is regarded as a uniform porous medium. [3] provided the local drag and heat transfer coefficient values required to close the transport equations. The conservation features of the finite volume method (FVM) were utilized to discretize the resulting partial differential equations. A preconditioned conjugate gradient approach was then used to solve the resulting system of semilinear equations. Excellent agreement between the predicted drag and heat transfer coefficient values in this paper and published data is observed.

[4] created a multi-scale model for two-phase modeling of multi-stream plate-fin heat exchangers. This model simultaneously takes into account important aspects of a multi-stream HX simulation, including phase change processes, multi-component mixtures, numerous streams, transversal, lateral, and longitudinal conduction, non-uniformity of incoming flow, varying fluid characteristics, and heat leakage. The resulting hypotheses are looked at: steady-state operation, minimal temperature variation along the plate thickness, known mass flow distributions that do not change with flow direction, and a greater emphasis on heat conduction within the solid than on conduction heat transfer across the fluid. In this study, the porous technique was not employed, and the computational elements discretized each domain and sub-domain of the exchanger. The governing equations are calculated independently for each domain, and the common boundary conditions handle thermal interactions.

Another case was simulated by Pozhilov and al. [5], for the heat and mass transfer in a 3D model of a loop heat pipe evaporator. This simulation included the model of Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes equations describing the flow in the liquid and vapor regions, Darcy's law for filtration modeling in the wicks (porous structure) and the energy equation with an accurate coupling of connected sub-domains that includes the effects of evaporation on interfaces between the porous and vapor regions.

Pozhilov et al. [5] simulated another scenario involving the mass and heat transmission in a three-dimensional model of a loop heat pipe evaporator. Darcy's law for filtration modeling in the wicks (porous structure), the Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes equations model defining the flow in the liquid and vapor regions, and the energy equation with an

accurate coupling of linked sub-domains incorporating the effects of evaporation on interactions between the porous and vapor regions were all included in this simulation.

In [6], a CFD model using a commercial software is developed for simulating the transport phenomena, especially the phase change, in a plate-fin heat exchanger. The flow channels, ducts and passes of the cold box, are considered in the computational geometry. The porous media simplification is introduced in the computational domain due to the excessive increase in the number of computational grids when the fins accounted for in the numerical domain. A flash calculations technique is used with CFD in evaluation of chemical species in the cold box by a user function in this case. This study also looks at the importance of local thermal equilibrium between the porous medium and fluid flow without mass transfer, local thermal equilibrium between the porous medium and fluid flow with mass transfer (LTE), and local thermal non equilibrium between the porous medium and fluid flow with mass transfer (LTNE).

4. Model description

4.1. Macro model: Multi-phase porous model

This approach (multiphase mixture model) models the fluid phases by solving the transport equations for mass, momentum and energy for the mixture of phases. For phase distribution: volume fraction transport equation for each phase.

Phase volume fraction transport equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \alpha_i dV + \oint_A \alpha_i v_m \cdot da \\ = \int_V (S_{u_i} - \frac{\alpha_i}{\rho_i} \frac{D\rho_i}{Dt}) dV \\ + \oint_A \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_i \rho_m} \nabla \alpha_i \cdot da \\ - \int_V \frac{1}{\rho_i} \nabla \cdot (\alpha_i \rho_i v_{d,i}) dV \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Mixture continuity transport equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho_m dV + \oint_A \rho_m v_m \cdot da = \int_V S_u dV \quad (2)$$

Mixture momentum transport equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho_m v_m dV + \oint_A \rho_m v_m \otimes v_m \cdot da \\ = - \oint_A p I \cdot da + \oint_A T_m \cdot da + \int_V S_u dV \\ + \int_V f_b dV - \sum_i \int_A \alpha_i \rho_i v_{d,i} \otimes v_{d,i} \cdot da \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Mixture Energy transport equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho_m E_m dV \\ + \oint_A [\rho_m H_m V_m + p + \sum_i \alpha_i \rho_i H_i v_{d,i}] \cdot da \\ = - \oint_A q \cdot da + \oint_A T_m \cdot v_m \cdot da \\ + \int_V (f_b \cdot V_m + S_u) dV \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

4.1.1. Porous model

The first characteristic of a porous medium is its porosity: this is the ratio between the volume not containing solids and the total volume of the medium V:

$$\epsilon = \frac{V_f}{V} \quad (5)$$

In the porous domain, the pressure losses are defined by the Darcy-Forchheimer law, for the ΔP in the x-direction it yields:

$$\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x} = -\frac{\mu}{k} u - \rho k_1 u^2 \quad (6)$$

With k the permeability and k_1 the inertial permeability, the permeability of a porous material is its capacity to let a fluid pass through it. A good permeability therefore implies a good porosity, but the opposite is not necessarily true, it has been shown to be intrinsic to the solid matrix of the porous medium and therefore only a function of its topology and its associated geometric properties.

the porous geometric parameters for this channel are the following:

ϵ	k	k_1
0.87	7.6e-8	78

Table 1: Porous parameters

The heat transfer in the porous media is treated with a local thermal non-equilibrium which yields the following energy formulation on solid and fluid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \chi \rho_f E_f dV + \oint_A \chi \rho_f H_f v \cdot da \\ &= - \oint_A \chi q \cdot da + \oint_A \chi T \cdot v \cdot da \\ & \quad + \int_V a_s h_s (T_s - T_f) dV \\ & \quad + \int_V (\chi f_b \cdot v) dV + \int_V S_u^e dV \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

with T, the solid temperature:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \int_V ((1 - \chi) \rho_s E_s) dV da \\ &= - \oint_A (1 - \chi) q \cdot da \\ & \quad + \int_V a_s h_s (T_s - T_f) dV + \int_V S_u^e dV \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Heat transfer between the solid matrix and the fluid:

$$\pm h_s a_s (T_s - T_f) \quad (9)$$

The purpose of this work is to define, in the case of a mini-channel plate-fin exchanger, the source in volume fraction of vapour S_u^i in the associated transport equation (the exchange coefficient h_s representing the convective exchange between the fluid and the porous matrix).

4.2. Micro model: Volume of fluid

This modelling approach consists of an interface capture method that predicts the distribution and movement of the interface of separate phases. It assumes that the resolution of the mesh is sufficient to resolve the position and shape of the interface between the phases. Fluids in the same cell containing the interface are treated as a mixture.

$$\alpha_i = \frac{V_i}{V} \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i = 1 \quad (11)$$

Transport equation volume fraction:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \alpha_i dV + \oint_A \alpha_i v \cdot da = \\ & \int_V (S_{\alpha_i} - \frac{\alpha_i}{\rho_i} \frac{D\rho_i}{Dt}) dV \\ & - \int_V \frac{1}{\rho_i} \nabla \cdot (\alpha_i \rho_i v_{d,i}) dV \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Transport equation on mass mixture:

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\int_V \rho dV) + \oint_A \rho v \cdot da = \int_V S dV \quad (13)$$

Transport equation on momentum mixture:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} (\int_V \rho v dV) + \oint_A \rho v \otimes v \cdot da \\ &= - \oint_A p I \cdot da + \oint_A T \cdot da \\ & \quad + \int_V \rho g dV + \int_V f_b dV - \\ & \quad \sum_i \int_A \alpha_i \rho_i v_i \otimes v_i \cdot da \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Transport equation on energy mixture:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho E dV \\ & + \oint_A [\rho H v + p + \sum_i \alpha_i \rho_i H_i v_{d,i}] \cdot da \\ &= - \oint_A q \cdot da + \oint_A T \cdot v da \\ & \quad + \int_V f_b \cdot v dV + \int_V S_E dV \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

4.2.1. Phase change model

The Rohsenow boiling model (this model is mainly used for low temperature boiling, but a film boiling model can be incorporated for higher temperature boiling) and the transition model (from nucleated boiling to transition) are the main models for modelling boiling flows. The empirical Rohsenow correlation is used to calculate the surface heat flux due to boiling:

$$q_{bw} = \mu_l h_{lat} \sqrt{\frac{g(\rho_l \rho_v)}{\sigma}} \left(\frac{C_{pl}(T_w - T_{sat})}{C_{qw} h_{lat} Pr_l^{n_p}} \right)^{3.03} \quad (16)$$

In this equation, μ_l , h_{lat} , C_{pl} , ρ_l , Pr_l and are the dynamic viscosity, latent heat, specific heat, density and Prandtl number of the liquid phase, n_p is the exponent of the Prandtl number, σ is the surface tension coefficient at the liquid-vapour interface and C_{qw} is an empirical coefficient which varies with the liquid-surface combination.

5. Test case description

In order to capture the flow regime in the channel, the "Volume of fluid" interface tracking model described in 4.2 is used. This modelling approach consists of a method that translates the distribution and movement of the interface of distinct phases (it assumes that the resolution of the mesh is sufficient to resolve the position and shape of the interface between the phases).

The representative elementary channel is a 58 fin offset mini channel with the same geometry as the prototype evaporator that will be experimentally assessed. The dimensions of the channel and the fins are listed in table 2 and illustrated in figure 5.

	channel dimensions	fin dimensions
height	2.42mm	2.02mm
length	260mm	5mm
width	0.55mm	0.25mm

Table 2: Channel and fin dimensions

Figure 1: channel element

Figure 2: channels view

Figure 3: channels domain

A trimmed cells mesher was used for the fluid domain, with a boundary layer prism layer cells mesher at the walls. The average cell size is $2.5E-5$ m with a maximum cell size of $5E-5$, the prism layer mesh have a thickness of 0.05mm with a stretching factor of 1.3, the total number of cells is around 3M. The mesh is illustrated in figure 5.

Figure 4: Mesh on micro model

In the determination of the boiling law, the effects of fin conduction are overlooked so a isothermal condition is applied at the solid walls. The boiling fluid used is the R134a. A pressure condition of 3.3 bar is applied at the outlet and a mass flow condition of $6.75E-5$ kg/s at 265K and a mass quality of 0 is applied at the inlet. The solid temperature is varied from 279.5 K to 307.5K The complete list of simulations performed is provided in table 3.

Solid T (K)	Δ to saturation (K)
279.5	+2
281.5	+5
287.5	+10
292.5	+15
297.5	+20
302.5	+25
307.5	+30

Table 3: Solid isothermal conditions

6. Mass transfer law

For each of the seven VOF simulations performed, the gas volume fraction and the temperature are extracted with an "average per fin volume method" as in [2].

The mass flow of gas from one fin to the next over the total mass flow is fitted and then plotted to give the mass transfer law as a function of fluid temperature in the channel. It is also noted that the wall temperature increase, while giving higher gas fraction, follow the same trend as lower wall temperatures.

Figure 5: Fin volume discretization

Figure 6: ΔT and quality plot along the channel

with:

$$Quality = \frac{m_{vapor}}{m_{total}} \quad (17)$$

and

$$\frac{m_{vapor}}{m_{total}} = \frac{a_{vapor} * \rho_{vapor}}{\rho_{total}} \quad (18)$$

The results yields the following law (fig:7) as a function of the fluid temperature difference to saturation, the law shows two evaporation regimes and will be divided in two plots.

Figure 7: mass transfer law function of temperature

First part of the boiling curve yields the following law:

Figure 8: mass transfer law function of temperature: first trend

And the second part:

Figure 9: mass transfer law function of temperature: second trend

Second part of the boiling curve give a very low vapor creation compared to the first part, in this work fluid is considered almost entirely evaporated in the first part as the delta of vapor fraction from fin $n - 1$ to fin n is close to 0 therefore the second law yields a source terms of 0.

7. Results: VOF-MMP comparison

The boiling law derived from the VOF simulation as described in the previous section has been implemented in the porous equivalent of the channel element. Then the porous two-phase simulations were ran with the mixture multiphase model. The methodology is schematized in figure 10.

Figure 10: micro to macro model for porous multiphase

The VOF micro model simulation requires a 3 million cells mesh for a run time of 3h to reach a steady state while the MMP simulation in an equivalent porous domain can be ran on a 80k cells mesh for run time of around 20 minutes. The same simulation are performed, this time on the MMP porous model at the highest and lowest wall heating for comparison. The boundary conditions remains the same but the domain is now defined with the porous model described above in 4.1.

Figure 11: micro VOF computation domain to macro MMP computation domain

The mass transfer law tested on two cases, at low and high wall overheating gives the following results on fluid temperature and quality, at solid temperature of 279.5K in 12 and solid temperature of 307.5K in 13.

Figure 12: Comparison at $T_{solid}=279.5K$

Figure 13: Comparison at $T_{solid}=307.5K$

The law accuracy when modeling boiling at lower temperature, where fluid thermal equilibrium is reached within first fins, is good along the channel, with the highest derivation at the channel inlet where the fluid temperature is at the highest difference to the imposed wall temperature. The quality is still given with a maximum error of 15%.

8. Conclusion

Overall fitting from VOF to MMP gives an error under 20% in temperature and volume fraction. Highest deviation are found in the case of a higher wall overheating since thermal equilibrium is not reached until later, and we will therefore have more instationnarity effects occurring between the two simulations. In a future work this same methodology will be applied to a vertical configuration in order to account for multiple positioning of a heat exchanger. The law would ideally include more variables such as wall temperature, flow topology and solid temperature as well.

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References

- [1] A. Horvat, I. Catton, Development of an integral computer code for simulation of heat exchangers.
- [2] S. Whitaker, The equations of motion in porous media, *Chemical Engineering Science* 21 (3) (1966) 291–300.
- [3] A. Zukauskas, R. Ulinskas, Heat transfer in tube banks in crossflow.
- [4] R. Niroomand, M. Saidi, S. Hannani, A general multi-scale modeling framework for two-phase simulation of multi-stream plate-fin heat exchangers, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 156 (2020) 119730.
- [5] A. A. Pozhilov, D. K. Zaitsev, E. M. Smirnov, A. A. Smirnovsky, Numerical simulation of heat and mass transfer in a 3d model of a loop heat pipe evaporator, *St. Petersburg Polytechnical University Journal: Physics and Mathematics* 3 (3) (2017) 210–217.
- [6] A. Zargoushi, F. Talebi, S. Hosseini, Cfd modeling of industrial cold box with plate-fin heat exchanger: Focusing on phase change phenomenon, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 147 (2020) 118936.